

Synthesis and Screening of Antimicrobial and Anti-inflammatory Activities of Aryloxy Derivatives of Benzimidazoles

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BENZIMIDAZOLE is associated with various kinds of biological activities¹. Phenoxyacetic acid, phenoxypropionic acid and their derivatives are also reported to be biologically active². With an intention to prepare more active drugs we have synthesised some novel phenoxy-, bromophenoxy-, chlorophenoxy-, nitrophenoxyacetyl as well as propionylbenzimidazoles and have screened their antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activities.

Results and Discussion

Synthesised compounds are *N*-[2-(phenoxy/bromo/chloro/nitro/methyl-substituted-phenoxy)acetyl/propionyl]benzimidazoles. Their physical data of compounds are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (1–17)*

Compd. no.**	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Yield %	M.p. °C	Solubility	Mol. formula
1	H	H	H	60	149–51	MeOH	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃
2	H	H	H	75	55–58	CHCl ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃
3	Br	Br	Br	70	136–37	EtOAc	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃ Br ₃
4	Br	Br	Br	65	200–02	CHCl ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ Br ₃
5	Br	Br	H	75	84–86	MeOH	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ Br ₂
6	NO ₂	NO ₂	NO ₂	68	218–20	Acetone	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₂ N ₅
7	NO ₂	NO ₂	NO ₂	80	112–13	MeOH	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₅
8	NO ₂	H	H	60	72–74	MeOH	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃
9	H	NO ₂	H	66	134–36	EtOAc	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃
10	Cl	Cl	Cl	75	249–51	MeOH	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₃
11	Cl	Cl	H	77	102–03	MeOH	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂
12	Cl	H	H	68	178–80	MeOH	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂
13	Cl	H	H	62	276–77	MeOH	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ Cl
14	H	Cl	H	76	258–60	MeOH	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ Cl
15	CH ₃	H	H	60	78–79	MeOH	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃
16	H	H	H	67	169–70	MeOH	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃
17	H	CH ₃	H	64	164–65	MeOH	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃

*All compounds gave satisfactory results for C, H and N analyses.

**R=H for all except 2, 4, 7 for which R=CH₃; R₂=H for all, but for 16 R₂=CH₃; R₃=H for all, but for 12 R₃=Cl.

Ir spectra recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer, displayed principle peaks at $\approx$ 1 570, 1 365, 1 335 (aromatic nitro ring), 1 240, 1 200, 1 160 (C–O–C), 785, 740, 685 (aromatic substitution pattern), 1 630–1 640 (C–O–N), 1 600–1 575 (strong band, C=N) and 2 930–2 900 cm^{-1} (CH₂).

Antimicrobial activities: Compounds 1–17 were screened for the antimicrobial activities against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus anthracis* and *Proteus vulgaris*. The filter paper disc method³ was followed using ethanolic solution of the compounds and the standard reference antibiotic streptomycin (10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was used.

The compounds were screened for antifungal activity against *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Candida albicans* and *Fusarium oxysporium* by the standard technique³ using mycostatin 100 (unit/ml) as a standard.

Most of the compounds were found active against gram(–) bacteria but showed better activities against gram(+) bacteria. The bromo- and chloro-substituted compounds were antimicrobially very active.

Anti-inflammatory activity: Carrageenin induced rat paw oedema method was employed for evaluating the anti-inflammatory activity of compounds 1–17 at doses of 50 and 100 mg/kg body weight of albino rats. Rat paw oedema was produced by the reported method⁴. For recording the anti-inflammatory effect, the method of Bhat *et al.*⁵ was followed.

All the compounds were found to be more or less mild CNS depressant and produced atoxia and fast

respiration but the nitro-substituted compounds were very toxic and severely depressant. Chloro-substituted compounds showed better anti-inflammatory activity than the bromo and nitro compounds. The *ortho*- and *para*-nitro-substituted compounds showed less activity than the trinitro compounds. The phenoxy acetyl/propionyl and methyl substituted compounds did not show significant activity. All the active compounds showed peak effect after 2–3 h.

Experimental

The m.ps. were taken on a Toshniwal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected.

Aryloxyacetic/propionic acids: Equimolar quantities of various phenols and monochloroacetic acid as well as phenols and α -chloropropionic acid were separately heated with 20% NaOH (5 ml) and water (25 ml) on a water-bath and the solution was evaporated almost to dryness. The residue was cooled and acidified with hydrochloric acid to yield the free acid. The mixture was then extracted with ether/ethyl acetate which on evaporation yielded the products.

Aryloxyacetyl/propionyl chlorides: To a solution of phenoxy acid (0.046 mol in 25 ml EtOAc/MeOH) was added thionyl chloride (0.056 mol), and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 7 h. The excess thionyl chloride was then distilled off under reduced pressure to yield the products.

Aryloxyacetyl/propionyl benzimidazoles: To an ice-cold solution of benzimidazole (0.036 mol in MeOH), was added 4 N NaOH (5 ml) solution and the aryloxyacetyl/propionyl chloride was added dropwise with constant stirring to give the products. The separated amides were washed and purified over a column of silica gel and the purity was checked by tlc.

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